

CLASSROOM DISCIPLINE IN THE CONTEXT OF TEACHING

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Abstract: *The article is dedicated to the study of various researchers' viewpoints on the importance of managing classroom discipline throughout the lesson and explores the notion of classroom discipline in the context of teaching.*

Key words: *student behavior, teacher actions, classroom indiscipline, organizational and management processes, promoting cognitive changes.*

Classroom disruption is a major challenge faced by teachers (Simón & AlonsoTapia, 2016). Teachers direct a great deal of energy toward classroom disruption while trying to reach their instructional goals (Brouwers & Tomic, 2000; Espelage & Lopes, 2013; Grayson & Alvarez, 2008). Classroom disruption is indeed often indicated as one of the main causes of wasted classroom time (Tsouloupas, Carson, & Matthews, 2014) and as a foremost reason for teachers' emotional exhaustion (Carson, Plemmons, Templin, & Weiss, 2011). This issue is also responsible for teacher turnover (Tsouloupas, Carson, Matthews, Grawitch, & Barber, 2010), primarily in situations in which teachers perceive high levels of disciplinary problems and poor administrative support (Kersaint, Lewis, Potter, & Meisels, 2007). Rinke (2008), for instance, cites the following four studies suggesting that student discipline (the opposite of student indiscipline) is an "important predictor of teacher retention, commitment, and satisfaction" (p. 5): (1) Haberman and Richards' study (1990) suggests that teachers initially predicted that underachievers would be their main classroom problem before teaching but later considered student disruption as their main concern after teaching; (2) Ingersoll (2001) found that 18% of *teacher movers* and 30% of *teacher leavers* report indiscipline as the main cause of their resignation; (3) Rosenholtz and Simpson (1990) showed that the school-wide management of student behavior was significantly correlated with teachers' commitment to the profession; (4) Smith and Smith (2006) found that school violence was the main cause of attrition in the first five years of teaching. Notably, because teachers may be exhausted from addressing classroom disruption and because teaching time may be significantly

affected by classroom disruption, students' opportunities to learn are likely decreased (Cothran, 2003; Sun, 2015). Classroom discipline clearly is a complex issue that cannot be reduced to a technical and/or scientific problem. Classroom discipline encompasses complex interactions among teacher variables, student variables, school variables and societal variables (e.g., general attitudes and values towards schooling). In fact, because classroom discipline is structured around the parceling of power in a specific public space, the issue becomes important politically and educationally (Buzzelli & Johnston, 2001; Pane, Rocco, Miller, & Salmon, 2014). Thus, the specific link between school goals and students' compliance is subject to political and ideological interpretations. These different interpretations are very clearly expressed in the classical division between a format of classroom management (or schools) in which the power is teacher-centered versus a classroom management format in which power is shared with the students (student-centered perspectives) (Ding, Li, Li, & Kulm, 2010; Evrim, Gökçe, & Enisa, 2009; Lau et al., 2006; Lewis, Romi, Qui, & Katz, 2005; Mullarkey, Recchia, Lee, Shin, & Lee, 2005; Psunder, 2005). In general, classroom indiscipline (or misbehavior) can be thought of as the behavior or behaviors that conflict with teaching (the primary vector of the class) and that the teacher attempts to correct through his actions (Doyle, 1985, 1986). Classroom discipline is therefore a breach of the management actions undertaken by the teacher to enable student learning. Basically, classroom discipline refers to a set of teacher actions that constitute organizational and management processes aimed at establishing classroom order (routines, norms, procedures, etc.). Discipline, in turn, refers to the actions that the teacher undertakes to end indiscipline and to restore order. It must be stressed, however, that although students are by far the most frequent source of indiscipline (Kulinna, Cothran, & Regualos, 2006), they are not the only source. The teacher or school staff may also be a source of disruption (Doyle, 1980; Good & Brophy, 2000). Thus, the issue of classroom discipline can be studied under a number of close designations such as "classroom order", "classroom misbehavior", "classroom disruption", "classroom indiscipline", or "classroom disorder", just to name a few. To discuss the myriad features involved in classroom discipline is beyond the scope of any book chapter. Therefore, this lesson will review only certain relevant but often overlooked issues related to classroom discipline.

Classroom discipline in the context of teaching

Classroom discipline is not a straightforward concept. The concept is even ill-defined because it is prone to multiple and subjective interpretations (Espelage &

Lopes, 2013). The concept of classroom indiscipline (the opposite of classroom discipline) seems more easily definable but is seldom used in the international literature. Whether we discuss discipline or indiscipline, it is useful to approach these concepts in the framework of the general task of classroom teaching.

Classroom teaching involves at least two different but intertwined features of a teacher's classroom action: the first feature has to do with the teacher's behaviors to promote cognitive changes (i.e., learning) in students; the second feature creates the organizational conditions that allow learning to occur. Learning promotion is closely related to: (1) the knowledge of subject matter and (2) how the teacher transmits the subject matter to the students. This feature of teaching, as a whole, is usually known as "instruction". However, the way in which a teacher organizes the transmission of content is usually labeled "didactics" (the part of pedagogy that addresses teaching methods). Notably, students learn as individuals, not as a group, even if most classroom teaching assumes a whole-group format. The second feature of classroom teaching has long been known in the literature as classroom order (Doyle, 1986). According to Doyle (2006), "From an ecological perspective, classroom management is about how order is established and maintained in classroom environments" (p. 99). Ecological models view classrooms as behavioral settings that can be divided into segments. Each segment is characterized by a specific activity, by a specific arrangement of participants, by a specific format of participation, etc., and has a specific vector or program of action (Doyle, 2006; Osher, Bear, Sprague, & Doyle, 2010). From this perspective, the main management goal of the teacher is to involve students in the specific programs of action during a class session and/or to create in the students a sense of belonging to that particular class. To fully understand the importance of classroom order with regard to student learning, it is useful to conceptualize classrooms as micro-organizations in which countless interactions occur during a class session. Classrooms are crowded places that demand clear rules, procedures and routines so that instruction can take place (Hochweber, Hosenfeld, & Klieme, 2014; Rogers & Mirra, 2014). Classroom order therefore refers to the set of procedures that the teacher develops to maximize the time devoted to instruction (Doyle, 1986). Classroom order, unlike what one might think, is only indirectly linked to and is conceptually independent of classroom disruption. The ultimate goal of classroom order is to enable instruction. Classroom order is not a goal in itself, nor is it a way to correct classroom disruption. Effective teachers have fewer classroom disciplinary problems not because they are good at restoring discipline, but because they are good at

establishing classroom procedures that maximize time available for instruction. These teachers tend, for instance, to keep up the lesson pace and to use the curriculum effectively to establish order and to maximize students' on-task behaviors. More effective teachers realize that a lesson that is too fast or a too slow pace may negatively affect students' focus on classroom tasks. Thus, they adapt the lesson pace to a specific curriculum, to the students' perceived knowledge, to the difficulty level of the subject being taught, etc.

In addition to mastering disciplinary contents, instruction/didactics and classroom order, teachers must also accomplish another vital task in the classroom: to restore classroom order when students' misbehaviors threaten the lesson flow (Emmer & Stough, 2001; Evertson & Emmer, 1982; Evertson et al., 2000; Freiberg, Templeton, & Helton, 2013; Kounin, 1977). Even the most effective teachers must occasionally address student misbehavior. However, research has also long shown (e.g., Bagley, 1907; Doyle, 1980; Kounin, 1977, 1983) that although there is not a significant difference in the way effective and ineffective teachers address classroom indiscipline, there is a notable difference in the way that effective and ineffective teachers manage the classroom. Specifically, effective teachers focus on teaching/instruction, whereas less effective teachers easily lose the lesson flow. Thus, the former maximize instructional time while the latter must address interruptions and off-task behaviors, thereby losing instructional time and energy. As Gore and Parkes (2007) eloquently state, "The literature has shown that a focus on relevant, engaging and stimulating curriculum coupled with challenging, engaging and supportive pedagogy...renders 'management issues' a far less troubling second place consideration" (p. 3). Unsurprisingly, teacher stress and burnout are far more likely to strike ineffective teachers (Curry & O'Brien, 2012; Košir, Tement, Licardo, & Habe, 2015; Ullrich, Lambert, & McCarthy, 2012). In sum, it is useful to conceptualize classroom (in)discipline in the framework of the overall task of classroom teaching or classroom management. Classroom (in)discipline can be conceptualized as a failure or a breakdown in classroom order and instruction. Theoretically, this means that when teachers focus on instruction (i.e., maintaining the lesson flow), they will have to address fewer disciplinary issues.

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